

The Liability of Maritime Carrier under the Iraqi Transport Law and International Conventions

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Abstract

Everywhere carriers incur a measure of liability for the safety of the goods. Carriers are liable for any damage or for the loss of the goods that are in their possession as carriers unless they prove that the damage or loss is attributable to certain excepted causes. Damaged and lost items can unfortunately be a common problem when shipping freight. Legal responsibilities arise due to loss or damage during transit while cargo is in their care. This study intends to investigate the nature of the liability of the maritime carrier when this liability is realized, and the extent to which it can be paid or disposed of given the risks realized from the transportation process, which may result in damage or loss of the goods, and the damage that may cause to the consignee because of this damage or loss.

Keywords: Maritime transport, Carrier liability, Cargo damage.

Introduction

Transport operations differ according to how they are carried out, It may be by planes, vehicles, or ships, and the maritime transport of goods in the field of international trade is the most common type of transport, as most of the international trade is handled through the sea, and this is based on the maritime transport contract, which has increased in importance with the development Maritime traffic, and with the tremendous development of ships, which increased in size and increased the degree of their absorption of goods, in addition to providing them with the latest equipment (Dowidar 2002).

In the contract for the maritime transport of goods, the marine carrier is considered the strongest economic party, through the conditions it dictates to the shipper in the shipping document, especially those that exempt him from liability in the event of loss or damage to the goods. These conditions caused severe damage to shippers, which led to disputes between shippers. The carriers, to reduce these disputes, several international agreements and treaties appeared, and perhaps the most important of them is the international agreement on unifying some rules related to bills of lading of 1924 called the Brussels Convention, and the Rotterdam Convention of 2008(AI-Smadi 2017).

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